

THE SYMBOL OF PATRIOTISM IN “DIGITAL FORTRESS”

BY DAN BROWN

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Abstract. This article provides an in-depth analysis of the work and discusses the digital security in the work, the lives of courageous individuals working for national security, and the dangers they face in their lives. Introductory part gives brief information about Dan Brown’s life and literary works and the role and place of “Digital fortress” work in the world literature and the history of writing this literary work. Moreover, the structure and conflict of the work, mainly characters are discussed, and their obligation to the motherland is shown in the main body. Giving detailed information, each of them is revealed separately. In the conclusion section all data are summarized.

Key words: Motherland, security system, mysterious, defensive tone, arrogance, bravery, patriotism, devotion.

Introduction. Dan Brown is in the list of the most prominent and a pen sharp writers, novelists of the English literature in this World. Furthermore, he is well known writer who proceeds a unique literary style of his awesome and inspirational works. This American novelist wrote well-researched and highly achievable novels that concentrated on secret organizations and had entangled plots in world literature. According to mass media, Dan Brown is the writer of countless the bestseller books, each of his literary works has already become one of the best readable famous novels

of all time and together with, the theme of psychic controversial among readers, specialists and scientists in the World.¹

There are some more works of him in which we can face with the detective style and elements. The writing of the literary work is due to an event that Dan Brown himself witnessed in his life and it changed this writer's lifetime. Dan Brown was arrested by the U.S. National Security Agency agents after he emailed a student friend at the University where he was teaching and working that he was joking about plotting to assassinate the U.S. president. The National Security Agency is one of the most secretive agencies whose job is to monitor citizens. This situation intrigues him and he decides to write a book about electronic security. When he came home and started writing, a virus came in via email and burned his computer's hard drive. Concerned, Dan Brown decided to publish a sensational book about the National Security Agency and its brave spies.

Literature review. According to comments which were given by M.W. Frazier who is a professor of politics in China institute, he wrote some notes to add in his own research “The power of place: contentious politics in twentieth-century Shanghai and Bombay” this techno-thriller novel focuses on overcoming contemporary digital technology that belongs to NSA and its abilities and function in preserving the safety in a country and mostly showing their code-breaking power . Moreover, as this book is pre-eminent and consistent it still has been so famous during 2 decades after its publishing² . John J. Nance explains his own thoughts on his works “Pandora's Clock”, “The Last Hostage” below:

“Digital Fortress is an exciting and initial, contentious feelings from writer Dan Brown. With its impressing plot Digital Fortress is an excellent sample of the techno-thriller literary works. But its some unique facets makes Digital Fortress stand out from the other literary works are its other elements: a real love legend that opens being

¹ Dan Brown. Digital fortress. Tashkent: Offset print, 2019.-p 2.

² <https://www.amazon.com/-/es/Dan-Brown/dp/0312944926>.

loyal and an trial of the struggles between affection and dishonesty. I consider this novel as a mix of loyalty and mendacity”³.

Analysis and discussion. One of the main characters of this novel is Susan Fletcher. Susan Fletcher also has both round and static characters because she has a multi-dimensional personality and her lifestyle is very complex and she did not change her perspectives in order to stop digital fortress the whole time. She is the head cryptographer of the NSA. She is the only woman among all the protagonists in the story, the youngest employee and extremely beautiful and absolutely gorgeous woman. This character is beautifully portrayed by the author as an extraordinary woman working under pressure. She is distinguished by the fact that in the process of a literary work she draws the reader's attention to her difficult situation. This woman is not only extremely beautiful, but also very brave and loyal to her obligation. She develops the whole plot with her defensive emotions for her sweetheart David Becker, a university professor and linguist. Although he wants to know what is NSA and her duties there, she does not tell anything.

“ ...Susan explained how the intercepted transmissions often originated from dangerous governments, hostile factions, and terrorist groups, many of whom were inside U.S. borders. Their communications were usually encoded for secrecy in case they ended up in the wrong hands—which, thanks to COMINT, they usually did. Susan told David her job was to study the codes, break them by hand, and furnish the NSA with the deciphered messages. This was not entirely true. Susan felt a pang of guilt over lying to her new love, but she had no choice. A few years ago it would have been accurate, but things had changed at the NSA. The whole world of cryptography had changed. Susan’s new duties were classified, even to many in the highest echelons of power. “Codes,” Becker said, fascinated”⁴.

This action delights the reader with its romantic and loyal relationships, as well as the techno-exciting episodes in the story. Furthermore, she is loyal with her job and

³ John J. Nance The Last Hostage. New York , 2015.

⁴ Dan Brown. Digital fortress. New York: St. Martin’s press, 1998-p 9.

also with her boss with obeys what her boss told and ordered anything was tough to do it to her.

“...Spain. I sent David to Spain. The commander’s words were stung. “David’s in Spain?” Susan was incredulous. “You sent him to Spain?” Her tone turned angry. “Why?”. Strathmore looked dumbfounded. He was apparently not accustomed to being yelled at, even by his head cryptographer. He gave Susan a confused look. She was flexed like a mother tiger defending her cub. ... Susan was lost. “What are you talking about?” Strathmore sighed. “Tankado surely would have had a copy of the pass-key on him when he died. I sure as hell didn’t want it floating around the Seville morgue.” “So you sent David Becker?” Susan was beyond shock. Nothing was making sense. “David doesn’t even work for you!”... Susan stared at Strathmore in disbelief. It was as if she no longer knew the man she was talking to. He had sent her fiancé—a teacher—on an NSA mission and then failed to notify the director about the biggest crisis in the history of the organization. ...In that instant, Susan realized what she respected so much about Trevor Strathmore. For ten years, through thick and thin, he had always led the way for her. Steadfast. Unwavering. It was his dedication that amazed her-his unshakable allegiance to his principles, his country, and his ideals. Come what may, Commander Trevor Strathmore was a guiding light in a world of impossible decisions. “You are on my team, aren’t you?” he asked. Susan smiled. “Yes, sir, I am. One hundred percent.” “Good. Now can we get back to work?” (page 27-28).

During the discussion, it should be noted that this work, together with the protagonists of the story, teaches devotion to the motherland, its supremacy, as well as sacrifice for the motherland. The novel bestows on every young reader the highest qualities of devotion, virtues of loyalty. I think that this work is important in making each of us, every soldier, every citizen feel their duty to the homeland.

Conclusion: Digital Fortress is a pretty fast-paced literary work with many actions and setting on both fronts. As usual with Dan Brown's novel, things get a bit unbelievable and ridiculous at times, but that’s part of what makes them fun. He was able to create an interesting ranges of characters, the best paradigms and mysterious

postures that really keep the storyline moving along at his usual break-neck pace over the world.

Every character in this novel can give moral instruction to a reader. It is considered a work of patriotism, responsibility, a strong sense of patriotism, courage and bravery and how to cope with difficult times.

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